

**Examining the performance and size
profiles of actively managed Mutual Funds
versus Exchange-Traded Funds in Portfolio
Management**

1.1: Synopsys.

About topic:

50,000,000,000,000 crore rupees and counting, is the size of Mutual Funds in India.

(association of mutual funds in india, n.d.)

In a world of rising living costs and high inflation rates, saving up money in cash form or the more famous bank FDs just doesn't lie with the long-term investment goals of today's investors. The appetite for risk in one's financial portfolio can yield high returns in both the short and long term but despite this risk one should invest their money in a more reliable and better investing instrument that will require good portfolio management.

The two significant players have emerged in the vast field of investment opportunities: i.e., mutual funds and exchange-traded funds. These players have shaped the financial landscape and given investors a variety of ways to increase their wealth. For both seasoned investors and those entering the financial world for the first time, understanding these investment vehicles is increasingly important as the global economy continues to change.

Let us understand what these funds are and what are the key differences between the two.

“A mutual fund is an investment option where money from many people is pooled together to buy a variety of stocks, bonds, or other securities. This mix of investments is managed by a professional money manager, providing individuals with a portfolio that is structured to match the investment objectives stated in the fund's prospectus”. (HAYES, 2023)

Compared to buying a single stock or bond, investing in a mutual fund gives investors access to a wide variety of assets, which can help lower risk. The performance of the fund, smaller fees or expenditures, determines the returns that investors receive.

The manager of the fund oversees the portfolio, determining how to distribute funds across sectors, industries, companies, and so on following the fund's stated strategy. By grouping money into a large fund, investors can gain access to a professionally managed, diverse group of securities that they would not normally be able to access individually. Individual investors benefit greatly from mutual funds' diversification and ease of access.

“An exchange-traded fund (ETF) is a type of pooled investment security that operates much like a mutual fund. Typically, ETFs will track a particular index, sector, commodity, or other assets, but unlike mutual funds, ETFs can be purchased or sold on a stock exchange the same way that a regular stock can. An ETF can be structured to track anything from the price of an individual commodity to a large and diverse collection of securities. ETFs can even be structured to track specific investment strategies”. (CHEN, 2024)

An ETF, or exchange-traded fund, is named from the understanding that it is traded on a trading platform, which is similar to shares. The selling price of an ETF's share fluctuates during the trading day as they are purchased and sold in the marketplace. This differs from

mutual funds, which are not traded on an exchange and only trade once a day after the markets shut. Furthermore, ETFs are generally less expensive and more liquid than mutual funds.

An exchange-traded fund, or ETF, is a form of instrument that holds several fundamental assets rather than just one, as a stock does. Because ETFs contain numerous assets, they are a popular alternative for protection. ETFs can thus incorporate a wide range of investments, such as stocks, commodities, bonds, or a combination of these.

An ETF is a tradable security, which means that it possesses a price for its shares that makes it easy to buy and sell on platforms throughout the day, as well as can be sold quickly.

About Industry:

The mutual fund industry in India started in 1963 with the formation of Unit Trust of India, at the initiative of the Government of India and the Reserve Bank of India.

Since then the mutual fund industry has seen a lot of growth both by small investors and big financial institutions.

List of Top Mutual Funds providers in India.

S.No	Mutual Fund House	Assets Managed(as of 31/03/2023)
1.	SBI Mutual Fund	₹ 700,990.72 crores
2.	ICICI Prudential Mutual Fund	₹ 509,588.31 crores
3.	HDFC Mutual Fund	₹ 437,876.34 crores
4.	Nippon India Mutual Fund	₹ 287,827.85 crores
5.	Kotak Mahindra Mutual Fund	₹ 284,073.77 crores
6.	Aditya Birla Sun Life Mutual Fund	₹ 261,232.11 crores
7.	Axis Mutual Fund	₹ 226,881.21 crores
8.	UTI Mutual Fund	₹ 223,698.69 crores
9.	Bandhan Mutual Fund	₹ 111,592.46 crores
10.	DSP Mutual Fund	₹ 107,067.08 crores

(Top 10 AMCs in India 2024, 2024)

Exchange-traded funds (ETFs) began their journey in India way back in 2002, a lot later than mutual funds. When the first ETF by Nippon India Mutual Fund was launched in India on the Nifty 50 Index. The ETF was listed on the NSE on January 8, 2002, and day one witnessed trading of Rs. 1.30 crores on the NSE. (ABOUT ETFS, 2023)

(Anush Raj P, 2021)

List of top ETFs in India.

S.No	ETF	Fund Size
1.	CPSE ETF	₹27,483.13 Cr
2.	Kotak Nifty PSU Bank ETF	₹1,067.36 Cr
3.	Nippon India ETF Nifty PSU Bank BeES	₹1,490.56 Cr
4.	ICICI BHARAT 22 ETF	₹12,951.72 Cr
5.	Motilal Oswal Nifty Midcap 100 ETF	₹334.26 Cr
6.	ICICI Prudential Nifty Midcap 150 ETF	₹237.55 Cr
7.	Nippon India ETF Nifty Midcap 150	₹1,014.27 Cr
8.	Nippon India ETF Nifty Infrastructure BeES	₹49.51 Cr
9.	Nippon India ETF Nifty Dividend Opportunities 50	₹31.09 Cr
10.	UTI S&P BSE Sensex Next 50 Exchange Traded Fund	₹5.89 Cr

(Top performing ETFs, n.d.)

Objective of this study:

The objectives of this study are:

- **Main Goal:** To analyze and compare the performance, risk characteristics, and suitability of mutual funds and ETFs in the Indian market to assist investors in making informed portfolio management decisions.
- **Examine portfolio diversification:**
 - Evaluate mutual funds' and ETFs' portfolio diversification.
 - Compare the industry distributions and risks across both investment portfolios.
- **Suggest recommendations for investor portfolio management.**
 - Provide a summary of the results and provide simple suggestions to investors according to their risk tolerance, investment objectives, and time in the market.
 - Consider the general effectiveness of investing in mutual funds and ETFs for a variety of investors.

Review of literature:

The literature on mutual fund performance evaluation is enormous. A few research studies that have influenced the preparation of this project substantially are discussed in this section.

A most recent study undertaken by Kishore Kumar Das and Shahnawaz Ali in 2020 confirmed that the adoption of Digitalization in the mutual fund industry had shown a positive trend in the increased participation of retail investors. Distribution channels are making use of this financial advancement to make their work more efficient and investor-friendly.

Sharpe, William F. (1966) suggested a measure for the evaluation of portfolio performance. Drawing on results obtained in the field of portfolio analysis, economist Jack L. Treynor has proposed a new predictor of mutual fund performance that differs from virtually all previous models by incorporating the volatility of a fund's return in a simple yet meaningful way.

Bijan Roy, et. al., conducted an empirical study on conditional performance of Indian mutual funds. This paper employs conditional assessment of performance to a sample of 89 Indian mutual fund schemes. This paper compares the performance of various mutual funds using both the unconditional and conditional forms of the CAPM, the Treynor-Mazuy model, and the Henriksson-Merton model. The impact of including lagged information variables in the evaluation of mutual fund managers' performance is investigated in the Indian context. The findings indicate that using conditional lagged information variables improves the performance of mutual fund schemes by shifting alphas to the right and reducing the number of negative timing coefficients.

Zakri Y.Bello (2005) matched a sample of socially responsible stock mutual funds matched to randomly selected conventional funds of similar net assets to investigate differences in characteristics of assets held, degree of portfolio diversification and variable effects of diversification on investment performance. The study found that socially responsible funds do not differ significantly from conventional funds in terms of any of these attributes. Moreover, the effect of diversification on investment performance is not different between the two groups. Both groups underperformed the Domini 400 Social Index and S & P 500 during the study period.

Kostovetsky (2003) found that the cost differences between index mutual funds and ETFs are due to management fees, shareholder transaction fees, tax efficiency, and other qualitative differences.

Research Methodology:

Data collection:

The data used in this research is secondary data taken from various reputable sources for the performance, risks and returns of various mutual funds and ETFs. The sites used include:

1. Moneycontrol.com
2. Etmoney.com
3. Valueresearchonline.com
4. Tickertape.in
5. Etc.

Performance analysis:

To analyse the performance of mutual funds and ETFs, the methods used in this study will be Average Annual Returns, Standard Deviations, and Expense Ratio for both mutual funds and ETFs.

Fee analysis:

Comparison will be drawn to expense ratios, management fees, and other hidden costs of mutual funds and ETFs. And calculation of the impact of fees on long-term returns.

Visualization and Presentation:

Use of charts, graphs, and tables to present the findings. Comparison of funds visually and highlighting key differences in performance, risk, and fees.

Practical Implications:

The study of differences between mutual funds and exchange-traded funds (ETFs) in the Indian market has important practical consequences for investors, financial advisers, and policymakers. They are as follows:

Investor Education and Decision Making:

The research can provide investors with valuable insights into the unique characteristics, risks, and benefits of mutual funds and ETFs. With this knowledge, investors can make more informed decisions that are consistent with their financial objectives, risk tolerance, and investment preferences.

Portfolio Diversification Strategies:

Understanding the differences between mutual funds and ETFs enables investors to strategically diversify their portfolios. For example, if an investor values intraday trading flexibility and low expense ratios, they may prefer ETFs. Individuals who prioritise professional fund management and automatic reinvestment may prefer mutual funds.

Risk Management and Asset Allocation:

This study helps to evaluate the risk characteristics of both investment Instruments. Investors can tailor their asset allocation strategies to their risk tolerance and market conditions, optimising portfolios for a balanced risk-return profile.

Cost Considerations:

The analysis of expense ratios and other associated costs sheds light on the overall cost-effectiveness of mutual funds and ETFs. Investors can consider these costs when making investment decisions, ensuring that the chosen investment fits within their budget and returns expectations.

Market Dynamics & Trends:

Retail investors who have just started their journey in the investment market can use the findings on mutual fund and ETF market dynamics and trends. This knowledge can be used to make decisions, thereby contributing to the creation of an environment that promotes healthy investments.

Industry Competitiveness and Evolution:

This study adds to our understanding of the competitive landscape between mutual funds and ETFs. This understanding can motivate industry players to fine-tune their offerings, increase transparency, and improve investor services in order to remain competitive in an evolving market.

Scope for further study:

The present research comparing mutual funds and exchange-traded funds (ETFs) in the Indian market sheds light on their performance, risk characteristics, and suitability for investors. However, several avenues for future research can help us better understand these investment vehicles and contribute to academic and practical knowledge.

Behavioural Analysis:

Future research could look into investors' behavioural aspects, specifically how behavioural biases influence the decision between mutual funds and ETFs. Understanding investor psychology can provide valuable insights into decision-making processes and assist in tailoring financial products to better meet investor needs.

Impact of Market Conditions:

It would be beneficial to investigate how different market conditions affect the relative performance of mutual funds and ETFs. Examining how these investment instruments perform in various periods of markets and economic environments can help investors make more dynamic and adaptable portfolio decisions.

Economic and Regulatory Influence:

A comprehensive study could look into how economic factors and regulatory changes affect the performance and adoption of mutual funds and ETFs. Changes in economic indicators, tax policies, or regulatory frameworks can have a significant impact on investor behaviour and the competitive landscape of these investment opportunities.

Global Comparative Analysis:

Broadening the study by including a global comparison would provide a more comprehensive perspective. Comparing the performance and adoption of mutual funds and ETFs in various international markets provides information on the factors that go beyond geographic limits and those that are unique to the Indian financial landscape.

Technology Innovations and Fintech Integration:

Given the rapid advancements in financial technology, future research could look into how technological innovations, such as fintech applications, affect the accessibility and appeal of mutual funds and ETFs. Understanding how these technologies affect investor engagement and product development is critical in a digitalized financial ecosystem.

Long-term Performance Analysis:

A longitudinal study that follows the long-term performance of mutual funds and ETFs over time may reveal trends, patterns, and potential shifts in the competitive dynamics between these investment vehicles. This would provide investors with information about the sustainability and consistency of returns.

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1.2: Mini Project.

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Hashim yasin (BBA-2214504046)
Manipal University Jaipur

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Section I:

Mutual Funds:

Mutual funds are a popular and easily accessible form of investment that allows individuals to collectively pool their money and invest in a diverse portfolio of stocks, bonds, and other securities. Professional fund managers manage this collective investment structure, making it an appealing option for investors looking for diversification, professional management, and easy access to financial markets.

How Mutual Funds Work:

Mutual funds operate under this simple principle: combining funds contributed by multiple investors in order to create a fund. The mutual fund company employs professional fund managers to manage this fund. Investors purchase mutual fund shares, and their value is determined by the fund's net asset value or NAV, which is calculated by the end of the trading day. The collective funds are invested in a diverse portfolio of assets, which may include stocks, bonds, money market instruments, or any combination of these.

Diversification helps to spread risk and reduce the impact of underperforming assets on the entire portfolio. Investors thus indirectly own a part of every stock in the mutual fund they are investing in.

Categories of Mutual Funds:

Equity Funds:

These types of funds mainly invest in stocks, hoping for profits. They can be further classified according to market size, such as large-cap, mid-cap, and small-cap funds.

Bond Funds:

These funds prioritise fixed-income securities, such as government or corporate bonds. They are considered less risky than equity funds, but they provide lower returns. Examples: ICICI Prudential Corporate Bond Fund, Nippon India Corporate Bond Fund, LIC MF Bond Fund Growth, Etc.

Money Market Funds:

These funds invest in short-term, liquid securities such as Treasury bills and commercial paper. They are less risky and provide lower returns than equity and bond funds. Examples: HDFC Money Market Fund, SBI Savings Fund, Aditya Birla Sun Life Money Manager Fund, Etc.

Index Funds:

These funds seek to replicate the performance of a specific market index, such as the NIFTY 50 or NIFTY 500. They provide broad market exposure at lower management fees than actively managed funds.

Sector Funds:

These funds focus on specific industries, such as technology, healthcare, and energy. While they can provide high returns, they also carry higher risk due to a lack of diversification. Examples include UTI Transportation and Logistics Fund, Reliance Pharma Fund, ICICI Prudential Technology Fund, Franklin Build India Fund, Reliance Banking Fund, Etc.

(Best Sector Mutual Funds, n.d.)

Hybrid or balanced funds:

These funds invest in a combination of stocks and bonds, ensuring a balanced approach to risk and reward. Examples include Quant Multi Asset Fund, Bank of India Mid & Small Cap Equity & Debt Fund, HDFC Balanced Advantage Fund, JM Aggressive Hybrid Fund, Etc.

(Hybrid Funds, n.d.)

Advantages of mutual funds:**Diversification:**

One of the primary advantages of mutual funds is diversification. Mutual funds diversify risk by investing in a variety of assets, reducing the impact of underperforming securities on the overall portfolio.

Professional management:

Experienced and knowledgeable fund managers make investment decisions on behalf of investors in mutual funds. This professional management can be especially useful for people who do not have the time or expertise to actively manage their investments.

Liquidity:

Mutual funds are typically liquid investments, allowing investors to buy or sell shares on any business day at the current NAV. This allows for flexibility and quick access to funds when needed.

Accessibility:

Mutual funds are available to a wide range of investors, regardless of their investment or financial background. Minimum investment requirements are frequently reasonable, making them an appropriate choice for beginners.

Cost efficiency:

While mutual funds may charge fees, they can be less expensive than building a diversified portfolio of individual securities. Index funds, in particular, are known for having low expense ratios.

Considerations and Risks:**Fees and expenses:**

Mutual funds usually charge fees, such as management fees, sales charges, and other costs. Investors need to be aware of these expenses and how this may affect their total returns.

Market Risk:

While diversification helps to reduce risk, mutual funds are still susceptible to market fluctuations. Economic conditions, interest rates, and geopolitical events can all have an impact on how the underlying securities perform.

Lack of control:

Investors hand over control of specific choices of investments to the fund manager. While this is great for those seeking professional management, it also means that investors have limited oversight of individual holdings.

Tax implications:

Investors in mutual funds may be subject to capital gains taxes even if they have not sold their shares. This is due to the fund manager buying and selling securities within the fund, which could result in capital gains for investors.

Exchange Traded Funds:

An ETF is a type of investment fund and exchange-traded product that consists of a portfolio of assets such as stocks, bonds, or commodities. Unlike traditional mutual funds, ETFs are traded on stock exchanges, offering investors a distinct combination of diversification, liquidity, and cost-effectiveness.

Evolution & Origins:

The concept of ETFs dates back to the early 1990s, when the American Stock Exchange (now NYSE) introduced the first ETF, the Standard & Poor's Depositary Receipts, also known as the "Spider." SPDRs tracked the performance of the S&P 500 index and quickly became popular among investors due to their simplicity and cost-effectiveness.

(A Brief History of Exchange-Traded Funds, n.d.)

ETFs have expanded their reach over time, now covering a wide range of asset classes such as equities, fixed income, commodities, and even alternative investments. Their success has fueled global proliferation, with exchanges around the world hosting a plethora of ETFs catering to a wide range of investment objectives.

(top 10 etf by asset class, n.d.)

Key Features of ETFs:

Liquidity:

ETFs are traded on stock exchanges during the trading days, just like individual stocks. This real-time trading capability provides liquidity to investors, allowing them to buy or sell shares at market prices during working hours.

Diversity:

ETFs typically hold a basket of underlying assets and provide investors with immediate diversification. This can lessen the impact of underperforming individual securities and lower overall portfolio risk.

Low expense ratios:

One of the most appealing aspects of ETFs is their affordability. Because of their passive management style, many ETFs have lower expense ratios than actively managed mutual funds.

Transparency:

ETFs disclose their holdings daily, so investors can see exactly what assets they own. This transparency builds trust and gives investors the information they need to make informed decisions.

Tax efficiency:

ETFs are structured to reduce capital gains distributions, making them tax-efficient investment vehicles. This is especially advantageous for long-term investors who want to maximise their after-tax returns.

Types of ETFs

Equity ETFs:

Equity ETFs are investment funds that seek to replicate the performance of a specific stock market index, such as India's Nifty 50 and its various versions. Investors can purchase shares in an equity ETF to gain exposure to a diverse portfolio of stocks that closely resembles the

composition of the underlying index. Equity ETFs in India include DSP Nifty 50 ETF, ICICI Pru Nifty 100 ETF, Nippon India ETF Nifty Midcap 150, Motilal Oswal Midcap 100 ETF, and Aditya BSL Nifty Next 50. *(Juzer Gabajiwala, n.d.)*

Bond ETFs:

Bond ETFs aim to provide investors with exposure to fixed-income securities such as debentures and government bonds, which have varying maturities. These ETFs provide an easy way for investors to invest in bonds without actually owning the underlying securities. Bond ETFs include government securities and the Nifty Bharat Bond. *(Juzer Gabajiwala, n.d.)*

Gold ETFs:

Gold ETFs were designed specifically to track the price of gold. Investing in gold ETFs allows investors to gain exposure to the price movements of gold without physically owning it. When compared to purchasing physical gold, gold ETFs are considered a more cost-effective way to invest in gold. Examples: Aditya Birla Sun Life Gold ETF, SBI Gold ETF, Kotak Gold ETF, Etc. *(Top & Best Gold ETFs In India 2024, n.d.) (Juzer Gabajiwala, aashika jain, n.d.)*

Sector ETFs:

Sector ETFs provide investors with exposure to specific economic sectors, such as technology, healthcare, and energy. These ETFs allow investors to benefit from the performance of a specific industry or sector without having to select individual stocks. Kotak IT ETF, ICICI Prudential Nifty Auto ETF, Axis Banking ETF, SBI ETF Consumption, and Aditya BSL Nifty Healthcare ETF are a few examples of such ETFs. *(Top & Best Gold ETFs In India 2024, n.d.)*

International ETFs:

Global Index ETFs track the performance of indices on foreign stock exchanges, allowing investors to diversify their investment portfolios globally. These ETFs offer exposure to global markets and can help investors reduce country-specific risks. Examples, are MOSL NASDAQ 100, HDFC World Index Fund, Mirae Asset NYSE FANG+ETF. *(Juzer Gabajiwala, aashika jain, n.d.)*

Advantages of ETFs:

Diversity:

ETFs provide fast diversification, lowering individual security risk while increasing overall portfolio stability.

Liquidity:

ETFs trade on exchanges like stocks, allowing investors to buy and sell shares at market prices throughout the trading day, resulting in liquidity and flexibility.

Transparency:

The full disclosure of ETFs ensures that investors have a clear understanding of the fund's holdings, encouraging trust and informed decision-making.

Low cost:

Passive management and the absence of frequent trading lead to lower expense ratios than actively managed funds.

Tax Efficiency:

One advantage of ETFs is that they are tax-efficient. ETFs use an "in-kind" formation and redemption process, which reduces capital gains distributions. This makes ETFs more tax-efficient than other investment vehicles.

Challenges and Risks.

While ETFs provide many advantages, investors should be aware of potential challenges and risks:

Market Risks:

ETFs are subject to market fluctuations, and their value may be influenced by factors affecting the underlying securities.

Tracking Error:

Some ETFs' performance may differ slightly from that of their underlying index due to factors such as fees, expenses, and market disruptions.

Liquidity risk:

As most ETFs are highly liquid, certain niche or less-traded ETFs may have lower liquidity, making it difficult to buy or sell at desired prices.

Complexity:

The total number of available ETFs can be overwhelming for investors. Making informed investment decisions requires a thorough understanding of each fund's specific objectives and risks.

Section II

Objective of the study:

The Indian mutual fund market is expected to develop at a CAGR of 21.5% by 2027, supported by increased digital penetration. Factors such as the robust performance of the equity markets and net inflows into equity schemes have resulted in significant industry expansion. The primary objective of this study is to provide a thorough examination of the performance, risk characteristics, and suitability of mutual funds and exchange-traded funds in the Indian market. This analysis is intended to provide investors with relevant insights, allowing them to make informed decisions about their portfolio management techniques.

Analyzing and Comparing Investment Instruments:

The study will conduct a thorough analysis of mutual funds and ETFs, including their performance, risk profiles, and suitability for various investing objectives. This analysis will be critical in putting light on the relative benefits and drawbacks of these two popular investing options.

Portfolio Diversification Evaluation:

The study will analyze the portfolio diversification strategies used by mutual funds and ETFs. This will entail determining how successfully these investment vehicles distribute their holdings across asset classes and businesses. The study's goal is to provide significant insights into mutual funds' and ETFs' diversification practices by analyzing industry distributions and risks.

General Effectiveness of Mutual Funds and ETFs:

Furthermore, the study will look at the overall efficacy of investing in mutual funds and ETFs for a wide spectrum of investors. The study's goal is to provide a full understanding of the potential benefits and downsides of these investment vehicles by evaluating their suitability for various investor profiles.

Recommendations for Investor Portfolio Management:

The results of the investigation will be used to develop realistic suggestions for investor portfolio management. These recommendations will be adapted to different risk tolerance levels, investment objectives, and market investment time frames. The study's goal is to allow investors to make well-informed decisions based on their specific financial goals and preferences by providing simple and straightforward recommendations.

Section III

Review of Literature:

Friend, Brown, Herman, and Vickers (1962) offered the first empirical analysis of mutual funds performance. Treynor (1965), Sharpe (1966), and Jensen (1968) developed the standard indices to measure risk-adjusted mutual fund returns. Grinblatt and Titman (1989b) constructed a positive period weighting measure of fund performance.

Sharpe, William F. (1966) suggested a measure for the evaluation of portfolio performance. Drawing on results obtained in the field of portfolio analysis, economist Jack L. Treynor has proposed a new predictor of mutual fund performance that differs from virtually all previous models by incorporating the volatility of a fund's return in a simple yet meaningful way.

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In a study conducted on November 2008 by Ilan Guedj and Jennifer Huang, The paper develops an equilibrium model that shows that ETFs and OEFs coexist in the market, catering to different types of investors with different liquidity needs and risk aversion. The paper also provides empirical evidence that ETFs have grown more in narrower, less liquid, and more concentrated indexes, where OEFs would have higher tracking errors and costs. And concluded that ETFs are better suited for investors with lower liquidity needs and higher risk aversion, while OEFs are more attractive for investors with higher liquidity needs and lower risk aversion.

A study conducted by Aron A. and Matthew R. (2007) found that emerging market mutual funds are influenced by both global and local factors, such as market integration, macroeconomic conditions, political stability, fund characteristics, and investor behavior. The

study also identified some gaps and limitations in the current research, such as the lack of consensus on the definition and classification of emerging markets, the heterogeneity and volatility of emerging market data, the challenges of measuring and comparing fund performance, and the need for more robust and dynamic models. The study suggested some directions for future research, such as exploring the role of alternative asset classes, incorporating more granular and timely data, applying machine learning and artificial intelligence techniques, and examining the impact of environmental, social, and governance factors on emerging market mutual fund performance.

A most recent study undertaken by Kishore Kumar Das and Shahnawaz Ali in 2020 confirmed that the adoption of Digitalization in the mutual fund industry had shown a positive trend in the increased participation of retail investors. Distribution channels are making use of this financial advancement to make their work more efficient and investor-friendly.

Section IV

Methodology and Data:

This study is going to examine the Mutual funds and ETFs listed in Indian stock exchanges.

The data taken into consideration for this study is secondary data collected from various sources and ranked based on a perceptive basis. The data is taken from the following sources:

1. Moneycontrol.com
2. Etmoney.com
3. Valueresearchonline.com
4. Livemint.com

Basic assumptions:

For the simplicity of calculations, we are going to take the Top 5 best-performing mutual funds from the large and small cap categories respectively only and on the ETF side, we are going to take the top 5 performing ETFs for January of 2024.

All sources of return, including price appreciation or depreciation, income from dividends or interest, and any distributions or capital gains are not accounted for in the report only the expense ratio is taken into consideration.

The methods that we are going to use to determine the risk and the performance of the funds will be:

- Total returns = Performance/Annual returns – Expense ratio. (Based on our assumption)
- The average rate of return for the category:

$$\text{Average return} = \frac{\text{Sum of Returns}}{\text{Number of Returns}}$$

- Standard deviation will help us in the determination of the risk to the performance of the fund.

$$\text{Standard deviation} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (R_i - \bar{R})^2}}{n-1}$$

Where,

R_i is the average return for each observation.

\bar{R} is the average return.

n is the total number of observations.

Selected large-cap funds:

The funds listed in this are selected based on their assets under management and have an AUM of 30,000cr.

Table, 1.1:

Sno.	Name of the fund (All Direct plans)	Fund house	Assets under management (AUM) in Cr.	Annualised 3-year returns (From, Feb 2021-2024)
1	ICICI Prudential Bluechip Fund	ICICI Prudential Mutual Fund	₹ 47928.62	20.51%
2	SBI Blue Chip Fund	SBI Mutual Fund	₹ 43487.36	15.54%
3	Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund	Mirae Assets Mutual Fund	₹ 37969.17	14.59%
4	Axis Bluechip Fund	Axis Mutual Fund	₹ 33171.04	10.92%
5	HDFC Top 100 Fund	HDFC Mutual Fund	₹ 30261.72	21.09%

Data as of February 2024

Sources: Money Control, Etmoney

Selected Gold ETFs:

The ETFs selected in this sample are benchmarked to gold (trying to mimic gold returns).

Table, 1.2:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Fund house	Assets under management (AUM) in Cr.	Annualised 3-year returns (From, Feb 2021-2024)
1	ICICI Prudential Gold ETF	ICICI Prudential Mutual Fund	4597.150	8.7%
2	HDFC Gold Exchange Traded Fund	HDFC Mutual Fund	4087.902	8.6%
3	SBI Gold ETF	SBI Mutual Fund	3592.171	8.6%
4	Axis Gold Exchange Traded Fund	Axis Mutual Fund	801.625	8.7%
5	Aditya Birla Sun Life Gold ETF	Aditya Birla Sun Life Mutual Fund	679.449	8.7%

Data as of February 2024

Sources: Scripbox, Etmoney

Selected Small Cap Funds:

The funds selected all have a minimum AUM of 10,000cr.

Table, 1.3:

Sno.	Name of the fund (All Direct plans)	Fund house	Assets under management (AUM) in Cr.	Annualised 3-year returns (From, Feb 2021-2024)
1	Quant Small Cap Fund	Quant Mutual Fund	₹ 13001.83	50.13%
2	Axis Small Cap Fund	Axis Mutual Fund	₹ 18615.72	31.66%
3	HDFC Small Cap Fund	HDFC Mutual Fund	₹ 26836.99	38.01%
4	Nippon India Small Cap Fund	Nippon India Mutual Fund	₹ 43815.61	41.82%
5	HSBC Small Cap Fund	HSBC Mutual Fund	₹ 13230.82	40.01%

Data as of February 2024

Sources: Money Control, Etmoney

Selected ETFs:

The ETFs selected in this sample hold the maximum Assets.

Table, 1.4:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Fund house	Assets under management (AUM) in Cr.	Annualised 3-year returns (From, Feb 2021-2024)
1	SBI Nifty 50 ETF	SBI Mutual Fund	174812.513	15.5%
2	UTI S&P BSE Sensex ETF	UTI Mutual Fund	36655.885	13.5%
3	CPSE ETF	Nippon India Mutual Fund	30526.233	56.3%
4	Nippon India ETF Nifty 50 BeES	Nippon India Mutual Fund	19300.799	15.6%
5	Kotak Nifty PSU Bank ETF	Kotak Mahindra Mutual Fund	1205.225	49%

Data as of February 2024

Sources: Scripbox, Etmoney

Case 1: Comparing a sample size of Mutual funds and ETFs that are known to be the safest in their category.

Table, 2.1:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Annual return (1 year)	Expense Ratio	Standard Deviation
1	ICICI Prudential Bluechip Fund	34%	1.53%	17.8%
2	SBI Blue Chip Fund	22.9%	1.54%	18.7%
3	Mirae Asset Large Cap Fund	21.7%	1.53%	17.9%
4	Axis Bluechip Fund	21.4%	1.57%	16.1%
5	HDFC Top 100 Fund	34.2%	1.66%	19.7%
Total Average return = Average Annual return – Average Expense ratio		25.23%		Average SD = 18.04%

Sources: Scripbox, Livemint

Table, 2.2:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Annual return (1 year)	Expense Ratio	Standard Deviation
1	ICICI Prudential Gold ETF	6.5%	0.5%	11.91%
2	HDFC Gold Exchange Traded Fund	7.3%	0.59%	11.91%
3	SBI Gold ETF	5.7%	0.65%	12.00%
4	Axis Gold Exchange Traded Fund	6.2%	0.56%	11.56%
5	Aditya Birla Sun Life Gold ETF	6%	0.54%	11.87%
Total Average return = Average Annual return – Average Expense ratio		5.772%		Average SD = 11.85%

Sources: Scripbox, Livemint

As we can see in the above case of our report in which we compared the 2 safest known categories in both Mutual funds and exchange-traded funds, i.e., The Large Cap Mutual funds invest in the top 50-100 companies and are benchmarked against the Nifty 50, Nifty 100, NiftyBank, Etc. On the ETFs side, the gold ETFs are benchmarked against gold-increasing prices, and they try to mimic these rates.

From the study above, we concluded that,

The Mutual Funds total return is larger than The ETFs, it may be inferred that the MF has produced more favourable returns overall during the given period. Several factors, including the investing methods of the fund managers, the particular assets held in each fund, and the state of the market, may be accountable for this behaviour.

An investment's return dispersion or volatility is measured by the standard deviation when ETFs and mutual funds' standard deviations are compared.

In the context of comparing Mutual Funds and ETFs, a higher standard deviation may indicate greater volatility in the investment and thus higher risk. Conversely, a smaller standard deviation can point to more consistent returns but fewer returns and lower risk.

In the case of the above study, the standard deviation is 18.04% in the case of Mutual funds, which is high but it can be said that it has given a considerably good return for the tradeoff of the risk it poses to the investment.

In contrast, the standard deviation of the ETF in the above study is 11.85% which in comparison to its return is twice as much, which means that the investment is at a risk of two times that of the profit that one can expect to gain from this investment.

Case 2: Comparing a sample size of Mutual funds and ETFs that are known to give the highest returns in their category.

Table, z2.3:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Annual return (1 year)	Expense Ratio	Standard Deviation
1	Quant Small Cap Fund	67.6%	1.71%	27.4%
2	Axis Small Cap Fund	41.3%	1.65%	19.5%
3	HDFC Small Cap Fund	55.3%	1.62%	23.8%
4	Nippon India Small Cap Fund	57.9%	1.51%	23.4%
5	HSBC Small Cap Fund	53.2%	1.71%	22.8%
Total Average return = Average Annual return – Average Expense ratio		53.42%		Average SD = 23.38%

Sources: Scripbox, Livemint

Table, 2.4:

Sno.	Name of the fund	Annual return (1 year)	Expense Ratio	Standard Deviation
1	SBI Nifty 50 ETF	25.4%	0.04%	13.42%
2	UTI S&P BSE Sensex ETF	21.8%	0%	13.47%
3	CPSE ETF	107.8%	0.05%	21.52%
4	Nippon India ETF Nifty 50 BeES	25.4%	0.04%	13.42%
5	Kotak Nifty PSU Bank ETF	75.5%	0.49%	35.07%
Total Average return = Average Annual return – Average Expense ratio		51.056%		Average SD = 19.38%

Sources: Scripbox, Livemint

As we can see in the second case of our report in which we compared the most return-giving instruments in their categories in both Mutual funds and exchange-traded funds, i.e, The Small Cap Mutual funds invest in companies that are up and coming and have a valuation of less than ₹5,000 crores.

On the ETFs side, the Equity ETFs are benchmarked against indices around the world like, Nifty 50, S&P 500, Nasdaq 50, Sensex, Etc.

In our second study above, we concluded that,

The total return given by The Mutual Funds is larger than The ETF we compared it to, it may be concluded that the Mutual fund has produced more favourable returns overall during the given period even though the ETF return lacks just **2.4%** behind the Mutual fund. Several factors, including the investing methods of the fund managers, the particular assets held in each fund, and the state of the market, may be accountable for this behaviour.

An investment's return dispersion or volatility is measured by the standard deviation when ETFs and mutual funds' standard deviations are compared.

In the context of comparing Mutual Funds and ETFs, a higher standard deviation may indicate greater volatility in the investment and thus higher risk. Conversely, a smaller standard deviation can point to more consistent returns but fewer returns and lower risk.

In the case of the above study, the standard deviation is **23.38%** in the case of Mutual funds, which is Very high and indicates a very high risk but when compared to its return of **53.42%** it can be considered by investors who seek this type of returns.

In contrast, the standard deviation of the ETF in the above study is **19.38%** which in comparison to its return of **51.056%** is comparatively better than the return provided by the Mutual fund for the same time frame and risk assessment.

Section V

Conclusion:

This study has concluded that Mutual Funds give better performance when compared to ETFs but that performance has its drawbacks as they come with the additional risk involved with the returns.

Despite the inherent limitations we will discuss below, this study contributes to a deeper understanding of the nuanced differences between mutual funds and ETFs. The findings underscore the importance of considering factors such as expense ratios, liquidity, tax implications, and risk-adjusted returns when making investment decisions.

While acknowledging the constraints of the study, it is evident that both mutual funds and ETFs offer unique benefits and trade-offs depending on investors' objectives, risk tolerance, and investment horizon. Therefore, a comprehensive evaluation of these factors is essential for investors to make informed decisions aligned with their financial goals.

Adding to this, future research endeavours could address the identified limitations and further explore additional factors influencing the performance and behaviour of mutual funds and ETFs. By continually refining our understanding of these investment options, we can better equip investors with the knowledge and insights necessary to navigate the dynamic landscape of financial markets effectively.

Finally, this study emphasises the value of data-driven analysis in informing investment decisions, as well as the need for ongoing research to better understand the roles of mutual funds and ETFs in investment portfolios. Using a strong analytical framework, investors can make well-informed decisions that are consistent with their financial goals and risk tolerance, maximising the potential for long-term wealth accumulation and financial prosperity.

Limitations:

This study has a lot of limitations as it only considered a small sample of data and that data also had a lot of presumptions about it.

The data presented in this study did not account for the Sharpe ratio, Alphas, and Betas as these would've complicated the mathematical aspect of the paper.

The sample size taken into study was very small but the reason it was taken is because these funds hold a majority of the total shareholder assets under them, so studying them was relatively easy and the data collection was easier because of the abundant data available on the internet about them.

The findings of the study are based on a specific time period and sample of mutual funds and ETFs. Generalizing the results to broader contexts or different market conditions may not be appropriate without further validation.

The study's findings are influenced by the market dynamics prevailing during the study period. Changes in economic conditions, regulatory environments, or investor sentiment could affect the performance and characteristics of mutual funds and ETFs differently over time.

The study may not fully account for investor behavior and preferences, which can significantly impact investment decisions. Factors like investor sentiment, market psychology, and fund flows could influence the performance and usage of mutual funds and ETFs.

This study doesn't guarantee that these trends may repeat themselves in future but this does give us an overview of what to expect when venturing into the investment world.

This study just gives us an overview of what to expect when trying to invest in an index fund.

Scope for further research:

The study of differences between mutual funds and ETFs in the Indian market has important practical consequences for investors, financial advisers, and policymakers. They are as follows:

Investor Education and Decision Making:

The research can provide investors with valuable insights into the unique characteristics, risks, and benefits of mutual funds and ETFs. With this knowledge, investors can make more informed decisions that are consistent with their financial objectives, risk tolerance, and investment preferences.

Portfolio Diversification Strategies:

Understanding the differences between mutual funds and ETFs enables investors to strategically diversify their portfolios. For example, if an investor values intraday trading flexibility and low expense ratios, they may prefer ETFs. Individuals who prioritise professional fund management and automatic reinvestment may prefer mutual funds.

Risk Management and Asset Allocation:

This study helps to evaluate the risk characteristics of both investment Instruments. Investors can tailor their asset allocation strategies to their risk tolerance and market conditions, optimising portfolios for a balanced risk-return profile.

Cost Considerations:

The analysis of expense ratios and other associated costs sheds light on the overall cost-effectiveness of mutual funds and ETFs. Investors can consider these costs when making investment decisions, ensuring that the chosen investment fits within their budget and returns expectations.

Market Dynamics & Trends:

Retail investors who have just started their journey in the investment market can use the findings on mutual fund and ETF market dynamics and trends. This knowledge can be used to make decisions, thereby contributing to the creation of an environment that promotes healthy investments.

Industry Competitiveness and Evolution:

This study adds to our understanding of the competitive landscape between mutual funds and ETFs. This understanding can motivate industry players to fine-tune their offerings, increase transparency, and improve investor services to remain competitive in an evolving market.

Section VI

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